

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**UPDATED RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ASSESSMENT AND
MANAGEMENT OF HYPERTENSION 2023**

Baraa Faiez Rajab¹, Fayeze Salem Alenzi², Ghadi Abdulaziz Jastaniah³,
Dalia Farouk Eltayeb Ahmed⁴, Haneen Anees Moumina⁵, Angie Magdie Felimban⁶,
Sarah Mohammed Alnassar⁷, Naglaa Abdallah Abdelrhman Siddig⁷,
Rami Sadakah A Mujahed⁸, Ayman Naji Khallaf⁹, Majed Mohammed Radhi Alsurayhi⁹,
Noor Haroon Sheikh¹⁰, Alaa Elmutaz Mohamed Mahmoud¹¹, Hassan Omar Qahwaji¹²

¹ King Abdulaziz Hospital-Jeddah – Saudi Arabia,² King Salman Hospital - Riyadh – Saudi Arabia,³ Ibn Sina National Medical College- Jeddah – Saudi Arabia,⁴ University of Khartoum - Khartoum – Sudan,⁵ King Abdulaziz University – Jeddah – Saudi Arabia,⁶ King Abdullah Medical Complex – Jeddah – Saudi Arabia,⁷ Barking, Havering and Redbridge University Trust (BHRUT) – London – United Kingdom,⁸ Maternity and Children Hospital – Makkah – Saudi Arabia,⁹ Medina Health Directory – Medina – Saudi Arabia,¹⁰ Alfaisal University - Riyadh– Saudi Arabia,¹¹ Nottingham University hospital - United Kingdom,¹² Health surveillance centers at Jeddah Islamic port- Jeddah – Saudi Arabia**Abstract**

Introduction: Hypertension, commonly known as high blood pressure, is a prevalent health condition that affects millions of individuals worldwide. Given its association with cardiovascular diseases, it is crucial to effectively assess and manage hypertension to prevent complications and improve patient outcomes. This paper provides an overview of the current recommendations for the assessment and management of hypertension, including diagnostic criteria, risk stratification, lifestyle modifications, pharmacotherapy, and monitoring strategies. By implementing these evidence-based guidelines, healthcare professionals can optimize the management of hypertension and enhance patient well-being.

Aim of the Study: The present review aims to understand the diagnostic criteria, risk stratification, lifestyle and pharmacological management of hypertension in adults.

Methodology: The review is a comprehensive research of PUBMED from 2003 to 2023.

Conclusion: A chronic condition known as hypertension affects millions of individuals worldwide. Many people have hypertensive blood pressure while strolling around and are unaware of it. The management of hypertension involves changing one's lifestyle, receiving pharmacological treatment, or using a combination of the two. Since hypertension affects numerous organ systems in the body, including the cardiovascular and renal systems, early diagnosis and treatment of the condition are essential to halting illness development. To ensure that the best course of treatment is followed, patients diagnosed with hypertension should regularly check in with their primary care physicians. To better meet the needs of patients, it is frequently necessary to alter drugs and lifestyle choices. Hypertension management is done individually, as patients have different risk factors and confounding variables that may contribute to their disease.

Keywords: ACE inhibitors, ARBs, Beta-blockers, calcium channel blockers, diuretic, hypertension, lifestyle modifications, low-sodium, management, risk-stratification, thiazide

Corresponding author:**Dr. Baraa Faiez Rajab,**

King Abdulaziz Hospital-Jeddah – Saudi Arabia,

baraarajab@gmail.com – 0556220311

QR code

Please cite this article in press Baraa Faiez Rajab *et al*, **Updated Recommendations For Assessment And Management Of Hypertension 2023.**, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2023; 10 (06).

INTRODUCTION:

Hypertension, commonly referred to as high blood pressure, is a chronic medical condition characterized by persistently elevated blood pressure levels. It is defined as a systolic blood pressure (SBP) of 130 mmHg or higher and/or a diastolic blood pressure (DBP) of 80 mmHg or higher. This definition is in accordance with the 2017 ACC/AHA guidelines for the prevention, detection, evaluation, and management of high blood pressure in adults.^[1] Hypertension is a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases such as heart attack, stroke, and heart failure.^[2] It is often asymptomatic, emphasizing the importance of regular blood pressure measurement to identify individuals with hypertension and initiate appropriate management strategies.

Further, almost 50% of hypertensive people do not have adequate blood pressure management. The classification of blood pressure levels serves as a guide for assessing the severity of hypertension and determining appropriate management strategies. The American Heart Association (AHA) and American College of Cardiology (ACC) have established the following classification system for blood pressure levels:^[3]

1. Normal: A systolic blood pressure (SBP) less than 120 mmHg and a diastolic blood pressure (DBP) less than 80 mmHg indicate normal blood pressure levels. Individuals in this category have a lower risk of developing hypertension and associated cardiovascular complications.
2. Elevated: Elevated blood pressure is defined as an SBP ranging from 120-129 mmHg and a DBP less than 80 mmHg. Although not classified as hypertension, individuals with elevated blood pressure are at increased risk of developing hypertension in the future. Lifestyle modifications are recommended to prevent the progression of blood pressure levels into the hypertensive range.
3. Hypertension Stage I: Hypertension stage I is characterized by an SBP between 130-139 mmHg

or a DBP between 80-89 mmHg. At this stage, lifestyle modifications and non-pharmacological interventions are typically initiated to manage blood pressure levels and reduce cardiovascular risk.

4. Hypertension Stage II: Hypertension stage II is diagnosed when the SBP is 140 mmHg or higher or the DBP is 90 mmHg or higher. Individuals with hypertension stage 2 often require pharmacological treatment, in addition to lifestyle modifications, to achieve blood pressure control and reduce the risk of cardiovascular events.

White coat hypertension, also known as white coat syndrome or white coat effect, refers to a phenomenon in which individuals experience elevated blood pressure readings when measured in a clinical setting, such as a healthcare provider's office, but have normal blood pressure levels in other settings. This condition is believed to be triggered by the anxiety or stress associated with the healthcare environment, leading to a temporary increase in blood pressure. It is estimated that white coat hypertension affects approximately 15-30% of individuals with elevated blood pressure readings in clinical settings.^[4]

White coat hypertension is important to recognize as it can lead to overdiagnosis and unnecessary treatment of hypertension. To differentiate white coat hypertension from sustained hypertension, ambulatory blood pressure monitoring (ABPM) or home blood pressure monitoring (HBPM) is recommended.^[5] ABPM involves wearing a portable device that automatically measures blood pressure at regular intervals throughout the day and night, providing a comprehensive picture of blood pressure patterns. HBPM involves self-monitoring of blood pressure at home using a validated device. By monitoring blood pressure outside of the clinical setting, a more accurate assessment of an individual's blood pressure status can be obtained, helping to determine the need for intervention or treatment.

It is important for healthcare providers to be aware of the possibility of white coat hypertension and consider ambulatory or home blood pressure monitoring for accurate diagnosis and appropriate management.^[6] By differentiating between white coat hypertension and sustained hypertension, unnecessary medication uses and associated potential side effects can be minimized, and individuals can be spared unnecessary treatment. Masked hypertension is a condition in which an individual's blood pressure appears normal when measured in a clinical setting, such as a healthcare provider's office, but is elevated outside of that setting. This phenomenon is the opposite of white coat hypertension and can lead to underdiagnosis and undertreatment of hypertension. Masked hypertension is estimated to affect approximately 10-20% of individuals with normal blood pressure readings in clinical settings.^[7]

The true prevalence and clinical significance of masked hypertension have gained recognition in recent years. It is associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular events, similar to sustained hypertension. Individuals with masked hypertension often have underlying risk factors, such as obesity, diabetes, or a family history of hypertension. Ambulatory blood pressure monitoring (ABPM) or home blood pressure monitoring (HBPM) is recommended to diagnose masked hypertension accurately. ABPM and HBPM provide a more comprehensive assessment of blood pressure patterns over a 24-hour period, including measurements during daily activities and sleep. These monitoring methods are valuable tools for identifying individuals with masked hypertension and initiating appropriate interventions to prevent future cardiovascular complications.^[8]

Healthcare providers should be aware of the possibility of masked hypertension, especially in individuals with risk factors or suspected white coat hypertension. By using ABPM or HBPM, healthcare professionals can identify masked hypertension, initiate lifestyle modifications, and consider pharmacological treatment to achieve blood pressure control and reduce the risk of cardiovascular events. Accurate identification and management of masked hypertension are vital in preventing long-term complications and improving patient outcomes.

Epidemiology

Hypertension, or high blood pressure, is a prevalent global health issue that affects a substantial portion of the population. As mentioned before, it is a leading risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, including heart

disease, stroke, and kidney disease. Understanding the epidemiology of hypertension is crucial for developing effective prevention and management strategies.

Hypertension has a significant global burden. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), in 2019, an estimated 1.13 billion people worldwide had hypertension. This represents about 1 in 4 adults globally. The prevalence of hypertension varies across countries and regions, with higher rates observed in low- and middle-income countries. However, hypertension is also a growing concern in high-income countries as well. This is mainly due to lifestyle changes, including sedentary behaviour, unhealthy diets, and rising obesity rates.

Age is also a significant risk factor for hypertension. The prevalence of hypertension increases with advancing age. In many populations, the prevalence of hypertension is higher among older adults. This highlights the importance of age-specific screening, diagnosis, and management of hypertension to prevent complications in this vulnerable population.

Furthermore, hypertension is associated with several risk factors and comorbidities. Obesity, physical inactivity, unhealthy diet (e.g., high sodium intake), excessive alcohol consumption, and tobacco use are among the modifiable risk factors for hypertension. Other conditions, such as diabetes, chronic kidney disease, and certain genetic factors, also contribute to the development and progression of hypertension.

The consequences of hypertension are substantial. Uncontrolled hypertension can lead to various health complications. It is a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, including coronary heart disease, heart failure, stroke, and peripheral artery disease. Hypertension is also associated with an increased risk of chronic kidney disease, retinopathy, and cognitive decline. Additionally, hypertension places a significant economic burden on healthcare systems due to the costs associated with managing hypertension-related complications and disabilities.

Overall, the epidemiology of hypertension highlights the need for population-level strategies to prevent and manage this condition. Promoting healthy lifestyles, including regular physical activity, a balanced diet, weight management, and reducing sodium intake, is crucial for hypertension prevention. Early detection, regular blood pressure monitoring, and appropriate management through lifestyle modifications and medications when necessary are essential in reducing

the burden of hypertension and its associated complications.

Etiology

The etiology, or underlying causes, of hypertension are multifactorial and can involve a combination of genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors. Understanding the various etiological factors is crucial for effective management and prevention of hypertension.

Genetic Factors: Genetic predisposition plays a significant role in the development of hypertension. Several genes have been implicated in blood pressure regulation, including genes involved in sodium transport, renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) regulation, and vascular function. Family history of hypertension is a strong risk factor, suggesting a hereditary component. However, the precise genetic mechanisms underlying hypertension are complex and not fully understood.

Lifestyle Factors: Certain lifestyle choices and behaviours contribute to the development of hypertension. Physical inactivity, unhealthy diet (e.g., high sodium, low potassium intake), excessive alcohol consumption, and tobacco use are major modifiable risk factors. Sedentary lifestyles and diets rich in processed foods, saturated fats, and refined sugars contribute to obesity, which is strongly associated with hypertension.

Renal Factors: The kidneys play a critical role in blood pressure regulation. Conditions affecting renal function, such as renal artery stenosis, polycystic kidney disease, and chronic kidney disease, can lead to hypertension. Impaired kidney function can disrupt fluid and electrolyte balance, sodium reabsorption, and hormonal regulation, contributing to elevated blood pressure levels.

Hormonal Factors: Hormonal imbalances can contribute to hypertension. Excessive aldosterone production by the adrenal glands, known as primary aldosteronism, can cause sodium and water retention, leading to increased blood pressure. Disorders of the thyroid gland, such as hypothyroidism or hyperthyroidism, can also influence blood pressure regulation.

Other Medical Conditions: Certain medical conditions and comorbidities are associated with hypertension. Diabetes, insulin resistance, and metabolic syndrome are closely linked to the development of hypertension. Obstructive sleep apnea, a condition characterized by

disrupted breathing during sleep, is also strongly associated with hypertension.

It is important to note that hypertension often occurs due to a combination of multiple factors, and the specific etiology can vary among individuals. Identifying the underlying etiological factors can help guide treatment decisions and lifestyle modifications to effectively manage and prevent hypertension.^[9]

Pathophysiology

The pathophysiology of hypertension, or high blood pressure, involves complex interactions between various physiological systems and underlying mechanisms. Although the precise mechanisms are not fully understood, several key factors contribute to the development and progression of hypertension. Factors affecting the disease include increased peripheral vascular resistance, sodium and fluid imbalances, renal abnormalities, and endothelial damage.

Increased Peripheral Vascular Resistance: One of the primary contributors to hypertension is increased peripheral vascular resistance. This occurs due to abnormalities in the small arteries and arterioles, which regulate blood flow and resistance in the peripheral circulation. Structural changes in the blood vessel walls, such as endothelial dysfunction, smooth muscle cell hypertrophy, and fibrosis, lead to decreased vessel elasticity and increased resistance, resulting in elevated blood pressure.

Sodium and Fluid Imbalance: Sodium plays a crucial role in regulating fluid balance and blood pressure. In hypertension, there is often an imbalance between sodium intake, renal sodium handling, and sodium excretion. Excess sodium in the body leads to increased fluid retention, expanding blood volume, and raising blood pressure. The renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) and the sympathetic nervous system play significant roles in regulating sodium and fluid balance and are frequently dysregulated in hypertension.

Renal Abnormalities: The kidneys play a vital role in long-term blood pressure regulation. In hypertension, there can be abnormalities in renal function and structure, leading to impaired sodium excretion and fluid balance. The RAAS, specifically the hormone aldosterone, is involved in regulating sodium reabsorption in the kidneys. Dysregulation of the RAAS can contribute to sodium and fluid retention, increasing blood pressure.

Endothelial Dysfunction and Inflammation:

Endothelial cells line the inner surface of blood vessels and play a critical role in maintaining vascular health. In hypertension, there is often endothelial dysfunction, characterized by impaired vasodilation, increased vasoconstriction, and enhanced inflammation. Endothelial dysfunction contributes to the development of atherosclerosis, oxidative stress, and vascular remodelling, all of which further increase peripheral resistance and raise blood pressure.

Symptoms

One of hypertension's nicknames is the "silent killer" because it typically does not cause noticeable symptoms in its early stages. Most people with hypertension are asymptomatic, which is why regular blood pressure monitoring is essential for early detection and management. However, in some cases, individuals with very high blood pressure may experience certain symptoms. Some symptoms include headaches, dizziness, light headedness, blurred vision, and chest pain. It is important to note that these symptoms are not exclusive to hypertension and can be caused by other underlying health conditions. Additionally, most people with hypertension do not experience any noticeable symptoms.

Diagnosis

Hypertension is a clinical diagnosis based on blood pressure readings. Accurate measurement of blood pressure is crucial for the diagnosis and management of hypertension. It is recommended to use validated devices and follow standardized techniques to obtain reliable blood pressure readings.^[10] The gold standard for blood pressure measurement is auscultatory or manual sphygmomanometer, where a healthcare professional uses a cuff, stethoscope, and a mercury or aneroid manometer to determine blood pressure levels. Automated oscillometer devices are also widely used and provide convenient and reliable measurements. Proper cuff size selection is essential, as using an incorrect cuff size can lead to inaccurate readings.^[11] Blood pressure should be measured in the sitting position with the arm supported at heart level after the patient has rested for at least 5 minutes. The management of hypertension is the most frequent cause of office visits and the use of chronic prescription drugs among non-pregnant individuals in the United States, where the prevalence of hypertension is high.^[12-13]

If a patient presents with hypertensive urgency or emergency (i.e. patient with systolic blood pressure ≥ 180 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 120

mmHg the diagnosis of hypertension can be made. Additionally, if a patient presents with systolic blood pressure ≥ 160 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 100 mmHg with known end organ failure, a diagnosis of hypertension can also be made. Note that these are two unlikely scenarios in patients without any known history of hypertension, however, they are still possible.

Further, in all other patients who have elevated blood pressure readings in a clinical setting (i.e. systolic blood pressure ≥ 130 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 80 mmHg), the diagnosis of hypertension can only be made using out-of-office measurements when possible. The gold standard of measuring blood pressure out-of-office is ABPM. Therefore, in order to diagnosis a patient with hypertension they must have elevated blood pressure both in the office and in an out-of-office setting.

Treatment

The treatment of hypertension aims to lower blood pressure and reduce the risk of cardiovascular complications. It typically involves a combination of lifestyle modifications and medications. Lifestyle changes are an essential component of hypertension management. Adopting the Dietary Approaches to Stop Hypertension (DASH) eating plan, which emphasizes fruits, vegetables, whole grains, lean proteins, and low-fat dairy products while reducing sodium, saturated fats, and added sugars. Additionally, limiting sodium intake to less than 2,300 milligrams per day (or even lower for certain individuals, such as those with diabetes or kidney disease). Another form of lifestyle modification includes engaging in regular aerobic exercise, such as brisk walking or cycling, for at least 150 minutes per week, or 75 minutes of vigorous activity. Further, achieving and maintaining a healthy body weight (body mass index between 18.5 and 24.9 kg/m²) can be very beneficial in the initial management of hypertension. Other forms of lifestyle changes include limiting alcohol consumption, quitting smoking and avoiding exposure to second hand smoke.

Medications are another common form of treatment for hypertension. Antihypertensive medications may be prescribed based on the individual's blood pressure level, overall health, and presence of additional risk factors or comorbidities. Diuretics are one class of antihypertensive medications. They include medicines such as thiazide diuretics, which help reduce fluid volume and lower blood pressure. Another class of antihypertensives are Angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors and angiotensin II receptor blockers

(ARBs). These medications block the effects of angiotensin, a hormone that narrows blood vessels, leading to vasodilation and reduced blood pressure. Calcium channel blockers can also be used in the management of hypertension. They work by relaxing blood vessels, allowing for better blood flow and lower blood pressure. Beta-blockers can be used to reduce heart rate and cardiac output, thereby lowering blood pressure. Depending on the individual's specific needs and response, other medications like alpha-blockers, central agonists, or direct renin inhibitors may be prescribed.

In some cases, multiple medications from different classes may be required to achieve blood pressure control. Combination therapy aims to target different physiological pathways involved in blood pressure regulation. It is important to note that the choice of medications and treatment strategies should be individualized based on factors such as age, comorbidities, and medication side effects. Regular monitoring of blood pressure and close follow-up with a healthcare professional are crucial for assessing treatment effectiveness and making necessary adjustments.^[14]

Randomized clinical trials have shown that treating hypertension with pharmacological therapy, as compared to placebo, has nearly a 50% relative risk reduction in heart failure, 30-40% relative risk reduction in stroke, and 20-25% relative risk reduction in myocardial infarction.^[15] Additionally, antihypertensive therapy has been shown to reduce relative risks to the same, if not greater extent in elderly hypertensive patients (over 65 years old). Because older patients have a higher total cardiovascular risk, even moderate and short-term blood pressure decreases may have bigger absolute benefits than those seen in younger people.

When deciding to start antihypertensive treatment in a patient, it is crucial to understand that the degree of blood pressure reduction, rather than the specific antihypertensive agent used, is the largest determinant in cardiovascular risk reduction for these patients. In order to reach their target blood pressure, the majority of hypertensive individuals will need to take multiple blood pressure medications. The availability of many blood pressure medication classes enables practitioners to customize treatment depending on unique patient features and preferences. Certain underlying medical conditions may require using one class of antihypertensives over another. However, if there are no contraindications, most guidelines recommend beginning with either of the following

four classes of medications: thiazide-like or thiazide-type diuretics, long-acting dihydropyridine calcium channel blockers, ACE inhibitors, or ARBs.

In patients with diabetic nephropathy or non-diabetic chronic kidney injury, ACE inhibitors or ARBs may be used as monotherapy when initiating antihypertensive treatment. Beta-blockers are less commonly used to initiate antihypertensive therapy unless specifically indicated such as in patients with ischemic heart disease or heart failure with reduced ejection fraction. Finally, race can also play a role in determining which antihypertensive agent to initiate. When used as monotherapy, the four drug classes mentioned before have similar efficacy in regards to cardiovascular risk benefits. However, combining an ACE inhibitor with a dihydropyridine calcium channel blocker has superior cardiovascular risk benefits when compared to combining the same ACE inhibitor with a thiazide diuretic.^[16] Seeing as many patients who begin with monotherapy will eventually need to have a second antihypertensive agent added, it would be more beneficial that in these cases the patient is started on either an ACE inhibitor or dihydropyridine calcium channel blocker then adding the other of the two is more beneficial than beginning with a thiazide diuretic then discontinuing it and adding an ACE inhibitor and dihydropyridine calcium channel blocker. However, thiazide diuretics are very effective when used as monotherapy alone and have added benefits in patients with osteoporosis, edema, or calcium nephrolithiasis with hypercalciuria. In patients with these specific conditions, thiazide-like diuretics (such as chlorthalidone and indapamide) have more benefits over thiazide diuretics such as hydrochlorothiazide.

When initiating antihypertensive therapy, patients should be evaluated by their healthcare provider every two to four weeks until their blood pressure goals are achieved. If at that point blood pressure is still uncontrolled, escalating the antihypertensive agent to at least half the maximum recommended dose should be done before adding an additional antihypertensive agent. Once blood pressure goals are met, patients can be followed every three to six months. Nonetheless, it is imperative that all patients with hypertension be followed closely by their physician at a regular basis.

CONCLUSION:

Hypertension is a chronic disease affecting millions of people around the world. There are many people walking around with hypertensive blood pressures and they do not even realize it. The causes of hypertension are multifactorial and the approach to management includes lifestyle changes, pharmacological treatment,

or a combination of the two. Medical management includes the use of diuretics, ACE inhibitors, ARBS, beta blockers, calcium channel blockers, and more. Diagnosis and treatment of hypertension early on is crucial to prevent progression of disease as it impacts many organ systems in the body such as the cardiovascular system as well as the renal system. Patients diagnosed with hypertension should follow up with their primary care physicians on a regular basis to ensure optimal therapy is achieved. Often, medications and lifestyle measures need to be modified to better cater to patients' needs. The approach to managing hypertension should be assessed on an individual basis as many different factors may contribute to the development of the disease.

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